

ANALYSES OF MECHANICAL REINFORCEMENT FOR CELLULOSE NANOFIBERS/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITES USING X-RAY DIFFRACTION

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Introduction

Cellulose is the most abundant renewable natural polymer on the earth. Nowadays, **cellulose nanofibers (CNF)** are receiving much attention because of their remarkable properties, such as light weight and high mechanical properties. Several methods for preparing CNF have been reported and these CNF with various fibrillation methods have different structures and properties. Therefore, it is important to investigate the dependence of their properties on their fibrillation processes for practical applications.

Montmorillonite (MMT) is a typical clay and can be dispersed in water, because of its hydrophilic surface. Thus, it can be expected that **CNF and MMT are compounded eco-friendly with simple mixing procedure in aqueous dispersion.**

We employed CNF as a matrix and MMT as a filler, then prepared CNF/MMT nanocomposites through mixing both aqueous dispersions. **Two types of CNF were prepared by mechanical (High-pressure homogenizer, FCN) and chemical (TEMPO-oxidization, TOCN) fibrillations** for evaluation of interaction between CNF matrix and MMT fillers. We used **"X-ray diffraction method"** [1] to investigate the reinforcement effect of MMT.

Matrix Cellulose nanofibers

- Light weight
- High mechanical properties
- Nano-scale dispersion in water

FCN
(Mechanical fibrillation)
TOCN
(Chemical fibrillation)

Filler Montmorillonite(MMT)

- 2-dimensional plate
- High reinforcement
- Nano-scale dispersion in water

Nanocomposites

- Excellent mechanical performance
- Environment-friendly

[Reinforcement effect analysis]

X-ray diffraction method

Stress transfer system

[1] T. Nishino et al., *Composites Part A*, 31,1225-1230 (2000).

Sample preparation

[2] A. Isogai et al., *Biomacromolecules*, 7, 1687-1691 (2006).

Mechanical properties

Stress transfer analysis

X-ray diffraction method

- Non-destructive
- *In situ*
- Quantitative

Fig. X-ray diffraction profiles of the MMT 060 reflection of the TOCN/MMT nanocomposite before and at loading.

- **Lattice spacing d**
 $2d \sin \theta = \lambda$
- **Crystal strain ϵ_c**
 $\epsilon_c = \frac{\Delta d}{d_0} = \frac{d_1 - d_0}{d_0}$
- **Stress on MMT σ_c**
 $\sigma_c = \epsilon_c \times E_{in-plane}$
($E_{in-plane}$: In-plane Young's modulus for MMT = 400 GPa [3])

Transferred stress σ_c to MMT

Fig. Relationship between the stress σ_0 applied to the FCN/MMT, FCN/MMT-N+Et₄, TOCN/MMT, TOCN/MMT-N+Et₄ and the stress σ_c on the MMT crystallites.

Fig. Relationship between the stress concentration coefficient σ_c/σ_0 and the Young's modulus of nanocomposites.

Conclusions

- The TOCN/MMT-N+Et₄ nanocomposite possessed the highest Young's modulus by the efficient reinforcement effect of MMT-N+Et₄ filler.
- Using X-ray diffraction method, **higher stress transfer efficiency** for TOCN/MMT-N+Et₄ was shown, which results in **higher mechanical performance** of the nanocomposite.

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